

Association of Perforated and Non Perforated Appendicitis with Age, Gender and Pre-Hospital Delay.

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Abstract

Background: Acute appendicitis is one of most common abdominal emergency with its peak incidence in extreme of ages. The risk of perforated appendicitis increases with delayed presentation to hospital. This study was conducted to determine association of perforated appendicitis with age, gender and mean duration between onset of symptoms and presentation to a tertiary care health facility.

Methods: This prospective cohort study was conducted at Surgical Unit of Holy Family Hospital, Rawalpindi, from May-August 2016 including 64 patients of Acute appendicitis presenting to the Emergency Unit. Their exposure statuses that were age, gender and pre hospital delay (in terms of duration of appearance of first symptom till presentation to hospital) was assessed through detailed history of patients. Then we followed these patients till their appendectomies and recorded types of appendicitis as outcomes, confirmed by the operating surgeons.

Results: 64 patients comprised of 32 males and 32 females (50% each). Overall mean age of 64 participants was 34.81 ± 17.33 years. Association between type of appendicitis and age, gender and pre hospital delay was determined and only statistically significant association was found between pre hospital delay of more than 12 hours and perforation of appendicitis with a relative risk of 6.45 (p-value 0.00, 95% confidence Interval 1.59-26.5).

Conclusion; The risk of perforation in Acute Appendicitis increases almost 6 times in patients with pre hospital delay. There is no significant association between perforated appendicitis and age or gender.

Key words: Age, Gender, Perforated, Appendicitis, Appendectomy, Hospital, Gangrenous.

Introduction

Acute appendicitis is one of the most common abdominal emergency. It affects approximately 250,000 patients each year¹, including 77,000 children.²

Appendicitis commonly presents with pain in right iliac fossa, nausea, vomiting and decreased appetite.³ Most commonly fecalith causes the obstruction of appendiceal lumen however, other causes include inflamed lymphoid tissue by viral infection, parasites, gallstones and tumors.⁴ The incidence of perforated appendicitis is higher in males (69.17%) as compared to females (30.82%).⁵ Delayed treatment also increases the incidence of complications.⁶

If appendicitis is left untreated, there is ischemic necrosis of appendiceal wall which leads to perforation (*perforated appendicitis*).⁷ Acute appendicitis may lead to complications like formation of an inflammatory mass, appendix abscess, or rupture, with generalized peritonitis.⁵ According to a research, obstruction is not an important causative agent of acute appendicitis but it might develop as an inflammatory process.⁸ Result of another research states that male sex, fever >38 C, anorexia and duration of pain in preadmission period were significant factors associated with perforated appendicitis and the risk of perforated appendicitis also increases with delayed presentation to hospital.⁹

The objective of our research was to determine the association of perforated appendicitis with age, gender and pre hospital delay in patients presenting to surgical unit of Holy Family Hospital Rawalpindi so that if we find any positive association we can provide evidence based recommendations of seeking prompt and early surgical consultations and interventions in case of suspected appendicitis, instead of delaying, going to quacks or taking analgesics in order to avoid complications. Thus timely diagnosis and management would assist in prevention of complications.

Methods and materials

It was prospective cohort study that was conducted from 14 May 2016 to 14 August 2016 in Surgical unit of Holy Family Hospital Rawalpindi. It included the patients who presented with acute appendicitis to emergency department of surgical unit of Holy family hospital during this duration. With the help of WHO Sample Size Calculator, keeping level of significance 5% and power of test 95%, minimally required sample size was calculated for all three study

variables and it was found to be 30 each for anticipated difference of proportion of gender groups, 41%¹⁰, 8 each for anticipated difference of proportion of pre-hospital delay 73.3%¹¹, and 32 each for anticipated difference of proportion of age groups 49%.⁵ We included 64 patients with 32 in each category of exposure. Non probability Consecutive sampling technique was used. In our study we had included the patients with acute appendicitis and excluded all those with negative appendectomies and incomplete data. Approval was taken from Institutional Research Forum and Ethical Review committee of RMC . From HFH Surgical unit, all patients fulfilling the above mentioned selection criteria were included in the study and their detailed history was taken regarding age, gender and pre hospital delay. Pre hospital delay was measured as the exact time period starting from the time when first of symptoms of acute appendicitis appeared till the time of presentation to hospital for each patient. Each of these patients were followed till their appendectomies were completed. Perforated and non perforated appendicitis was recorded as mentioned by the operating surgeons after completion of surgical procedure and were recorded in structured performas designed for this study. Statistical Package of Social Sciences version 22 was used for data entry and analysis. Frequencies and percentages were calculated for categorical variables like gender and for continuous variables like age and pre hospital delay, means along with standard deviation, mode and median were also calculated. Pearson’s Chi Square Test at 5% level of significance was applied. The p value <0.05 was considered statistically significant. Relative risks along with 95% confidence intervals were also calculated. Exclusion of value “1.00” from the confidence interval determined the statistical significance of relative risk.

Results

A study of total 64 patients comprised of 32 males (50%) and 32 females (50%). Overall mean age of 64 participants’ 34.81±17.33 years, the youngest being 8 years old and eldest 65 years of age. 32 patients were less than 40 years and 32 were greater than 40 years of age. Overall mean of Pre hospital delay was 39.09 ±47.90 hours, median and mode both were 12 hours. 32 patients presented with pre hospital delay of more than 12 hours and 32 patients presented with pre hospital delay of less than 12 hours. Out of 64 patient 49 (76.6%) had non perforated appendicitis and 15 (23.5%) had perforated appendicitis. Association were explored for gender, age and pre operative delay and only statistically significant association was observed between pre hospital delay and type of appendicitis (p=0.00) as displayed in table 1.

Table1. Association of age, gender and pre hospital delay with type of appendicitis.

Characteristics		Non perforated appendicitis f(%)	Perforated appendicitis f(%)	P value	Relative risk	Confidence intervals
Age	>40	24(75%)	8(25%)	0.76	0.87	0.36-2.12
	<40	25(78.1%)	7(21.9%)			
Gender	Male	25(78.1%)	7(21.9%)	0.76	0.87	0.36-2.12
	Female	24(75%)	8(25%)			
Pre hospital delay	<12 hr	30(93.8%)	2(6.3%)	0.00*	6.45	1.59-26.5
	>12 hr	19(59.4%)	13(40.6%)			

*highly statistically significant

Discussion

Acute appendicitis is the most common abdominal surgical emergency and shows different pathology, clinical causes, course and outcome in different patients.¹² When acute appendicitis progresses to perforation, the consequences often lead to prolonged and difficult convalescence or even to death.⁵ The results of our study showed that perforation of appendix is strongly influenced by the time lapse between the symptoms and the surgical interventional treatment but not affected by age and gender of the patient. Perforated appendicitis risk increases with increase in pre hospital delay. Perforated appendicitis may occur when appropriate treatment for acute appendicitis is delayed for a number of reasons, including problems with access to health care, failure by the patient to interpret symptoms as important, misdiagnosis and other delays in treatment.¹³ Gofrit ON and Abu-Daluk conducted a study on 581 patients and they found that total delay from symptom onset to surgery was 33 hours in non perforated group and 60 hours in perforated appendicitis group.¹⁴ In our study the mean pre operative delay was 44.35 hours for non perforated group and 57.12 hours for perforated group. According to our study 86.67% patients of perforated appendicitis presented to hospital after 12 hours of onset of symptoms and only 13.33% presented to hospital within 12 hours. A possible explanation for delayed presentation to hospital is the culture of reluctance to go to hospital, financial crisis, seeking medical advice from quacks and self medication. Extreme of ages may be considered as a risk factor for perforated appendicitis . In a study conducted by Toms Augustin, age more than 55 years is significant predictor of perforated appendicitis. In their study

patients older than 55 years, 29% had perforated appendicitis at 36 hours of symptoms and 67% at 36 to 48 hours of symptoms¹⁵. It is important to recognize that the clinical picture of acute appendicitis in young children is often atypical and confusing.¹⁶ Appendicitis is a more serious situation in elderly patients than in young one. The higher morbidity and mortality rates among the elderly undoubtedly reflect an increased prevalence of pre-existing cardiovascular and other diseases as well as a predictable decline in many physiological functions.⁵ Gurleyik G described that morbidity and mortality rates in elder patients with perforated appendicitis are comparatively higher than the other age groups and are 35.5% and 5.5% respectively.¹⁷ A delay in the presentation of the elderly patients to the hospital may result from difficulties in leaving home, fear of hospitalization, alteration in usual symptoms and diminished perception of them or diminished ability to express themselves effectively. In our study no significant relation is found between age and type of appendicitis. According to our study 46.67% patients of perforated appendicitis were of age less than 40 and 53.3% patients had age more than 40.

Male gender may be considered as a risk factor for perforation. The life time risk of appendicitis in males is 8.6% and in females 6.7%.^{18,19} According to a research conducted in department of surgery in Rajavithi hospital, college of medicine, Ranjits university there is increase risk of perforation in males.⁹ According to another study where appendectomies of 3186 males and 1764 females were compared; Males were somewhat more prone to perforation than were females, 25% versus 22% ($p = 0.016$). Conversely, the rate of normal appendices being found at the time of surgery was elevated significantly in females, 20% versus 9.4% ($p < 0.001$). Although there was no significant overall difference in the age distribution of males and females in this study ($p = 0.17$, t test). This most likely reflects the influence of the active-duty population.²⁰ In our study the risk of perforation is almost same for both genders. According to our study 53.33% patients of perforated appendicitis were males and 46.67% were female and there was no statistically significant relation between gender and type of appendicitis.

Conclusion

The risk of perforation in Acute Appendicitis increases with increase in prehospital delay. There is no significant association between type of appendicitis and age or gender.

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